

Microwave-induced cycloaddition of imines with acid chlorides in absence of a tertiary amine: Unprecedented synthesis of β -lactams in dimethylformamide

Ram Naresh Yadav^{a,b}, Ashlee Chavez^b and Bimal Krishna Banik^{b,c,d*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Faculty of Engineering & Technology, Veer Bahadur Singh Purvanchal University, Jaunpur-222 003, Uttar Pradesh, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, University of Texas-Pan American, 1201 W. University Dr., Edinburg, TX 78539, USA

^cThe University of Texas M. D. Anderson Cancer Center, Department of Molecular Pathology, 1515 Holcombe Blvd, Houston, TX 77030, USA

^dCurrent Address: Community Health System of South Texas, 3135 South Sugar Road, Edinburg, TX 78539, USA

E-mail: bimalbanik10@gmail.com, bimal.banik@chsst.org

Manuscript received 30 September 2018, accepted 01 November 2018

Synthesis β -lactams in N,N-dimethylformamide proceeds through cycloaddition of acid chlorides with imines in a domestic microwave oven in the absence of a tertiary base. This is an unprecedented observation.

Keywords: β -Lactams, cycloaddition, microwave, DMF.

Introduction

The application of clinically active β -lactam antibiotics and β -lactamase inhibitors has given chemists to design and synthesize new β -lactams¹. β -Lactams have been used as key compounds in the preparation of numerous heterocycles of scientific importance². Hydroxy β -lactam has been used in the semi-synthesis of anticancer drug, paclitaxel (Taxol) and docetaxel (Taxotere)³. β -Lactam has been discovered as drugs for lowering cholesterol⁴. As a result of diverse potentials, the searches for useful β -lactams have become one of the most active research areas for the past many decades^{5,6}.

The cycloaddition between acid chloride **2** and imine **1** in the presence of a tertiary base has been investigated for the preparation of β -lactams. Herein we report an unprecedented result that includes the synthesis of diverse monocyclic β -lactams following Staudinger cycloaddition reaction without using tertiary amine as a base in a domestic microwave oven.

Results and discussion

The synthesis of β -lactams using the Staudinger cycloaddition reaction was discovered more than hundred years ago.

For example, the reaction of acetoxy, alkoxy and nitrogen acid chlorides with diaryl imines produces either a *cis*, *trans*, or a mixture of *cis/trans* β -lactams in the presence of a tertiary base. It is important to note that the reaction does not proceed at all without the tertiary base. Microwave-induced reaction of β -lactam synthesis has also been used for this purpose. In many instances, microwave-induced reactions have altered the stereochemical results of the products and therefore, this method has become an important topic of research. In most of the instances, synthesis β -lactams is performed in organic solvents (dichloromethane, dichloroethane, THF, chlorobenzene, acetonitrile, toluene, and benzene). Based upon our on-going projects of synthesis and medicinal evaluation of β -lactams, our current idea was to investigate a reaction of acid chloride **2** and imine **1** in DMF in a microwave oven at relatively high temperature (approximately 100°C, Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Microwave induced synthesis of racemic monocyclic β -lactams.

Table 1. Synthesis of monocyclic (+/-)-*cis/trans* β -lactams via Staudinger ketene-imine [2+2] cycloaddition reaction under microwave condition

R ¹	R ²	R ³	3 4		Time (min)	Yield (%)
			<i>cis</i>	<i>trans</i>		
			ratio			
Phenyl	Phenyl	Acetoxy	3a+4a (3:7)		3	80
Phenyl	Phenyl	Methoxy	3b+4b (3:7)		3	90
Phenyl	Phenyl	Benzyloxy	3c+4c (5:5)		3	75
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Acetoxy	3d+4d (3:7)		3	80
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Methoxy	3e+4e (6:4)		3	90
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Benzyloxy	3f+4f (5:5)		3	80
Cinnamyl	Phenyl	Acetoxy	3g+4g (5:5)		3	90
Cinnamyl	Phenyl	Methoxy	3h+4h (8:2)		3	80
Cinnamyl	Phenyl	Benzyloxy	3i+4i (7:3)		3	80
Cinamyl	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Acetoxy	3j+4j (5:5)		3	80
Cinnamyl	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Methoxy	3k+4k (8:2)		4	80
Cinnamyl	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Benzyloxy	3l+4l (5:5)		3	90

This reaction resulted in an unprecedented observation. From the reaction, a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*- β -lactams were isolated, although tertiary amine was not used in the reaction.

Acetoxy, benzyloxy and methoxy acid chlorides were used along with diverse diarylimines. The microwave irradiation time was for 3–4 min. Most of the instances a mixture *cis*- and *trans*- β -lactams were obtained. Cinnamyl groups at the imines favored the formation of *cis*-isomer whereas aromatic groups favored the formation of the *trans*-isomers. Acetoxyacetyl chloride favored the formation of the *trans* compound whereas methoxyacetyl chloride favored the formation of the *cis* compounds. These *cis*- and *trans*- β -lactams were separated.

Staudinger cycloaddition reaction was used for the synthesis of some *trans*- β -lactams in the presence of a tertiary base using microwave irradiation and by changing the order of the addition of the reactants. In some examples, *trans*- β -lactams were formed from cyclic imines and polyaromatic imines.

Upon irradiation of the *cis*- β -lactams **3** in a microwave oven in DMF, no isomerization to *trans*-product **4** was observed. The present study confirmed that microwave irradiation can accelerate the synthesis of β -lactams. However, there were no differences in the yields of the products regardless the reaction was performed in a domestic and automated microwave oven (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Mechanism of β -lactam formation under microwave condition.

The mechanism of Staudinger reaction has been studied extensively. However, the rationale for the diastereoselectivity of β -lactam formation remains a challenging research topic. The stereoselectivity is depended on the components of the imine, acid-chloride, solvent, temperature, bases and other numerous conditions. In some examples, *cis*- β -lactam is formed exclusively or predominantly when acid chloride is added drop wise at low to room temperature to a solution of imine and a tertiary base. However, a *trans*- β -lactam becomes the major or exclusive product when a tertiary base is slowly added to the imine and acid chloride solution at high temperature. Computer-assisted energy calculation of the transition states is proposed to identify the origin of the stereochemical distributions. The intermediate structures are at-

tempted to verify by Infrared Spectroscopy. It is believed that cycloaddition of the imine takes place from the least crowded side of the ketene and this process produces zwitterion transition states. A conrotatory cyclization of the unstable intermediates finally leads to *cis*- and *trans*- β -lactams. Probably, the *trans*-isomer is formed through an isomerization process of the highly reactive intermediates enolates.

The same isomerization process may also occur because of high temperature and radiation effects exerted by the microwave. The aromatic groups at the nitrogen have the capacity to stabilize the iminium ion through rotation of the bond and this entire process leads to *trans*- β -lactam. If there is no isomerization of the iminium ion, *cis*- β -lactams become the products. Although the mechanism discussed above can explain the formation of *cis*- and *trans* β -lactam formation in the presence of a tertiary amine (or other tertiary amines), our current method is performed without a tertiary amine. It is assumed that DMF at high temperature and under microwave irradiation can undergo decarbonylation and this process generates dimethylamine in the reaction medium. Dimethylamine then reacts with acid chloride and generates ketene intermediate. Alternatively, it is believed that acid chloride liberates hydrochloric acid gas under the reaction conditions and this is capable of hydrolyzing the amide bond of DMF to generate dimethylamine. This suggests that DMF is a source of the tertiary amine that is necessary for the β -lactam synthesis by cycloaddition reaction as discussed. Notably, the method described herein is new and therefore, warrants numerous other investigations not only in this type of research, but also other related investigations.

Acknowledgement

BKB gratefully acknowledges the financial support for this research project from National Institutes of Health.

References and Notes

1. J. Buynak, *Curr. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **11**, 1951.
2. (a) M. S. Manhas, B. K. Banik, A. Mathur, J. E. Vincent and A. K. Bose, *Tetrahedron Symposium in Print*, 2000, **56**, 5587; (b) A. K. Bose, C. Mathur, D. R. Wagle and M. S. Manhas, *Tetrahedron Symposium in Print*, 2000, **56**, 5603; (c) I. Ojima, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1995, **28**, 383; (d) B. K. Banik, M. S. Manhas and A. K. Bose, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1994, **59**, 4714; (e) B. K. Banik, M. S. Manhas and A. K. Bose, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1993, **58**, 307.
3. (a) J. W. Clader, D. A. Burnett, M. A. Caplen., M. S. Domalski, S. Dugar, W. Vaccaro, R. Sher, M. E. Browne, H. Zhao, R. E. Burrier, B. Salisbury and H. R. Davis, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1996, **39**, 3684; (b) D. A. Burnett, M. A. Caplen, H. R. Darris (Jr.), R. E. Burrier and J. W. Clader, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1994, **37**, 17334; (c) D. A. Burnett, *Curr. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **11**, 1873; (d) J. W. Clader, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **47**, 1.
4. (a) A. E. Taggi, A. M. Hafez, H. Wack, B. Young, W. J. Drury III and T. Lectka, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 7831; (b) P. A. Magriotis, *Angew. Chem.*, 2001, **113**, 4507; (c) B. L. Hodous and G. C. Fu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 1578; (d) A. Cordova, S. Watanabe, F. Tanaka, W. Notz and C. F. Barbas, III, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 1866; (e) S. France, A. Weatherwax, A. E. Taggi and T. Lectka, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2004, **37**, 592.
5. (a) A. Arrieta, B. Lecea and F. P. Cossio, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1998, **63**, 5869; (b) F. P. Cossio, A. Arrieta, B. Lecea and I. M. Ugalde, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **116**, 208; (c) F. P. Cossio, J. M. Ugalde, X. Lopez, B. Lecea and C. Palomo, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **115**, 995; (d) L. S. Hegedus, J. Montgomery, Y. Narukawa and D. C. Snustad, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **113**, 5784.
6. R. Lopez, T. L. Sordo, J. A. Sordo and J. Gonzalez, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1993, **58**, 7036.

